

Title:**To grind or not to grind? The influence of mechanical and thermal treatments on the Cu/Zn disorder in $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSn}(\text{S}_x\text{Se}_{1-x})_4$ monograins****Authors:**

G. Gurieva^{1*}, V. Rotaru², K. Ernits³, N. Siminel⁴, A. Manjón-Sanz⁵, M. Kirkham⁵, A. Perez-Rodrigues^{2,6}, M. Guc², D. Meissner^{3,7}, S. Schorr^{1,8}

Affiliations:

¹ Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie, Berlin, Germany

² Catalonia Institute for Energy Research (IREC), Jardins de les Dones de Negre 1, 2^a pl., 08930 Sant Adrià del Besòs Barcelona, Spain

³ crystalsol OÜ, Akadeemia tee 15a, 12618 Tallinn, Estonia

⁴ Institute of Applied Physics, Academy of Sciences of Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

⁵ Neutron Scattering Division, Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Oak Ridge, USA,

⁶ Departament d'Enginyeria Electrònica i Biomèdica, Universitat de Barcelona, Martí i Franquès 1, 08028 Barcelona, Spain

⁷ Department of Materials and Environmental Technology, Tallinn University of Technology, Ehitajate tee 5, 19086 Tallinn, Estonia

⁸ Institute of Geological Sciences, Freie Universität Berlin, Berlin, Germany

* galina.gurieva@helmholtz-berlin.de

Abstract

Kesterite-type based thin film solar cell technologies are mainly based on polycrystalline absorber layers. A promising low cost alternative technology uses $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSn}(\text{S}_x\text{Se}_{1-x})_4$ (CZTSSe) monograins (single crystals of 20-100 μm size) which are fixed in a polymer matrix to form a flexible solar cell. The Cu/Zn disorder is discussed as a possible reason for band tailing causing voltage losses limiting the efficiency of CZTSSe-based devices. The experimental determination of the order parameter Q which is a quantitative measure of Cu/Zn disorder, requires a differentiation between the isoelectronic cations Cu^+ and Zn^{2+} . An in-depth analysis of neutron diffraction data allows the determination of type and concentration of intrinsic point defects including a distinction between Cu and Zn. Neutron diffraction requires large sample volumes, thus monograins offer the unique possibility to correlate structural disorder in CZTSSe with device performance parameters. In this study we tackle the influence of grinding the monograins on stoichiometry deviations, the Cu/Zn disorder as well as intrinsic point defects and optoelectronic properties of CZTSSe monograins. Moreover, an easy methodology based on Raman scattering spectroscopy is proposed for the assessment of Cu/Zn disorder in the CZTSSe compounds.

Introduction:

The compound semiconductors $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSn}(\text{S}_{1-x}\text{Se}_x)_4$ (CZTSSe), consisting of earth abundant and non-toxic elements, are an attractive low-cost alternative for the absorber layer in thin film solar cells. These compounds are called kesterites because they crystallize in the kesterite-type structure [1]. A new record power conversion efficiency of 13.5% for kesterite-based thin film solar cell was recently

obtained applying an off-stoichiometric absorber composition and Li doping [2]. Nevertheless, the low open circuit voltage with respect to the band gap phenomenon is considered as one of the main challenges of the kesterite-based solar cells. The absorber band tailing caused by the exceptionally high density of Cu_{Zn} and Zn_{Cu} anti-sites causing Cu/Zn disorder [3,4] is believed to be one of the reasons for the limited open-circuit voltage in CZTSSe-based devices [5]. However, possible improvements of the photovoltaic (PV) device parameters correlating with a reduced Cu/Zn disorder [6,7] have not yet been reported and the underlying mechanism limiting the device performance is still to be determined.

A number of strategies have been applied in order to avoid and/or decrease the level of Cu/Zn disorder in these compounds. Cation mutations aiming on substituting Cu with Ag, substituting Zn with Cd, Fe or Mn, even Ni, as well substituting Sn by Ge, some of them produce improvements to the overall performance in comparison to baseline reference cells, but none of them did lead to a record device [8]. Another strategy to decrease Cu/Zn disorder is a low temperature thermal treatment of the absorber layer. This method is based on the order-disorder phase transition occurring in $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_4$ (CZTS) at $T=260^\circ\text{C}$ [9] and in $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$ (CZTSe) at $T=200^\circ\text{C}$ [10].

The determination of the cation distribution on the structural sites in the kesterite-type structure, especially with respect to Cu^+ and Zn^{2+} has been approached in various ways [11], deducing indirectly the decrease of Cu/Zn disorder at temperatures below the order-disorder transition temperature: by anomalous lattice parameter expansion [12], Raman spectroscopy and spectrophotometry [9], electro-reflectance [13], and from kinetics simulations [11].

There is a huge gap between these studies and the fundamental understanding of Cu/Zn disorder in CZTSSe, as most of these studies are performed on thin films, by methods which can provide the access to the Cu/Zn disorder only indirectly. Polycrystalline thin film absorber layers are usually inhomogeneous, with an off-stoichiometric absorber composition and with secondary phases being present [14]. To separate Cu_{Zn} and Zn_{Cu} anti-site point defects causing Cu/Zn disorder from the other intrinsic point defects correlated to the off-stoichiometric absorber composition (e. g. vacancies, interstitials and anti-sites) is a very complex problem [15]. In order to determine Cu/Zn disorder in a direct approach and even more to quantify the level of disorder by an order parameter, it is necessary to locate the positions of Cu^+ and Zn^{2+} within the kesterite-type structure. In general, atomic positions and their occupancies are determined by X-ray diffraction methods, but in this case this is not a trivial task, as Cu^+ and Zn^{2+} are isoelectronic cations and thus have essentially the same X-rays scattering factor. Thus, they cannot be distinguished by conventional X-ray diffraction. Only few experimental methods allow tackling Cu/Zn disorder directly, most promising among them being anomalous X-ray diffraction and neutron diffraction. Neutron powder diffraction has been used to study the crystal structure, structural disorder and point defects in stoichiometric $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_4$, $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$, off-stoichiometric $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$ as well as $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnGeSe}_4$ and a number of other related compounds and solid solutions [1, 3, 4, 15-19]. The main disadvantage related to the use of neutron powder diffraction is the necessity of a sufficiently large probed volume of homogeneous material, which makes it inapplicable for structural investigations of CZTSSe thin films. Thus, the correlation of structural parameters, especially the cation distribution in the atomic structure, obtained by neutron powder diffraction and photovoltaic performance parameters of a solar cell is quite complicated.

A promising low-cost alternative PV technology uses CZTSSe monograins (single crystals of 20-100 μm size) which are fixed in a polymer matrix to form a flexible solar cell [20]. As neutron diffraction requires large sample volumes, kesterite monograin powders offer the unique possibility to correlate structural disorder in kesterite-type absorbers with performance parameters of a working photovoltaic device¹. But there are certain risks related to reliability of extracted information, as for performing X-ray

diffraction and as well as for the thermal treatment to decrease Cu/Zn disorder (“ordering” annealing) usually monograins are ground which can be seen as a mechanical treatment of the material. In the present work we applied neutron diffraction in order to reveal the distribution of Cu^+ and Zn^{2+} in the kesterite-type crystal structure to determine the concentration of Cu_{Zn} and Zn_{Cu} anti site defects in the CZTSSe monograins and deduce the order parameter Q of the Cu/Zn disorder [10]. The influence of the mechanical as well as the thermal treatment of the CZTSSe monograins on the Cu/Zn disorder and intrinsic point defect scenario, on other structural, vibrational and optoelectronic properties of the CZTSSe monograins were studied.

Experimental:

Grinding experiment and thermal treatment of CZTSSe monograins

The literature available at the moment suggests that a long annealing at temperatures well below the order-disorder transition is the key to decrease Cu/Zn disorder in CZTSSe [9-11]. A number of studies were devoted to the development of a perfect annealing procedure. But very few conclusions were strengthened by an order parameter determination applying direct methods. We decided to test such an annealing procedure additionally to the grinding on the $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSn}(\text{S}_x\text{Se}_{1-x})_4$ monograins.

The 6 samples used in this work were produced as follows: CZTSSe monograins (15 g) were grown following the standard monograin technology used at crystalsol OÜ and described previously in [20, 21]. In the next step the sample was divided in two parts, one part was ground in an agate mortar (sample names C15 – initial monograin and C15g – initial monograin ground). In the next step each of two parts was divided in three samples. One of the three from each part was not treated any more (sample names C15 and C15g). The other 4 samples were placed in sealed evacuated silica tubes for annealing (no grinding or pressing pellets at this step). For the thermal treatment all four ampoules were placed in the same one zone furnace, in order to have the same thermal history. First the temperature was increased with a rate of 50K/h to 300°C and held for 48h. Then two of the tubes (one as-grown and one ground) were taken out of the furnace and quenched in ice water in order to reach the state of complete disorder, or at least make the kesterite material as disordered as possible (these “disordered” CZTSSe are named C15Q and C15gQ with Q for quenching). The last two tubes were left in the furnace and the temperature was gradually reduced with a rate of 5K/h to certain annealing steps with constant temperature (see Figure 1). The lower was the annealing temperature, the longer was the holding time. This “ordering” annealing procedure was adapted from [10] in order to achieve a relative equilibrium at every annealing step (Figure 1). These slowly cooled CZTSSe is named “ordered” CZTSSe (sample names C15S and C15gS with S for slow). It has to be noted, that these four treated CZTSSe samples were never ground again. A schematic representation of the whole experiment can be found in Figure 1.

Wavelength dispersive X-ray spectroscopy

The phase content and chemical composition of the phases present in the monograin samples were determined by wavelength dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (WDX) using an electron microprobe analysis system (JEOL-JXA 8200) equipped with WDX unit. In order to obtain reliable results from the WDX measurements, the system was calibrated using elemental standards. High accuracy of the compositional parameters was achieved by averaging over 10 local measurement points within one grain and averaging over more than 40 grains of the CZTSSe phase. Averaging over all grains of this main phase is possible since deviations of the values for each of the measurements within each grain as well as among all of the grains did not exceed a 2% error, originated by the instrument. For the present secondary phase, $\text{ZnS}_x\text{Se}_{1-x}$ (Figure 2a), additional grains of this phase were measured in the

same way. The complete overview of the obtained cation ratios and deduced chemical composition of the two CZTSSe monograin samples is shown in Table I.

Neutron powder diffraction

For structural characterization of these monograins neutron powder diffraction was applied. Neutron powder diffraction experiments have been performed at the Spallation Neutron Source (SNS, Oak Ridge National Laboratory) using the POWGEN BL-11A powder diffractometer [22], IPTS 26264. Approximately 3-4 gram of powder samples were loaded in 6-mm diameter vanadium cans and loaded in the POWGEN automatic sample changer. Time of flight (T.O.F) data were collected at room temperature for 3-4 hours. A center wavelength of 1.5 Å was used, covering a d -spacing range of 0.485-13 Å. The data treatment was performed by a full pattern Rietveld refinement [23] using the FullProf Suite software package [24]. The kesterite type structure ($I\bar{4}$) with Cu on Wyckoff position $2a:(0,0,0)$ and $2c:(0,\frac{1}{2},\frac{1}{4})$, Zn on $2d:(0,\frac{1}{2},\frac{3}{4})$, Sn on $2b:(\frac{1}{2},\frac{1}{2},0)$ and S and Se on $8g:(x,y,z)$ was used as structural model in the refinement [3]. The refinement of site occupancy factors (SOF) was done without any chemical constraints.

Raman spectroscopy

The Raman spectra have been measured using a Horiba Jobin Yvon FHR640 monochromator coupled with a CCD detector in a backscattering configuration thorough the probe designed in IREC. The study was performed using a YAG:Nd solid state laser (532 nm, ~ 25 W/cm²) as excitation source, concentrated in a macro-spot with a diameter of about 70 μ m, which allowed collecting Raman spectra from several grains. This and the use of an un-polarized light beam allowed minimizing the influence of the crystalline orientation of the grains on the resulting Raman spectra. Moreover, the spectra of 9 points for each sample were measured allowing to obtain an average representative spectrum for each studied sample. The spectra were normalized on the position of the main peak of monocrystalline Si which was imposed to 520 cm⁻¹.

Diffuse reflectance spectroscopy

Diffuse Reflectance Spectroscopy (DRS) measurements were carried out in air at room temperature in a spectrophotometer equipped with an integrating sphere - Perkin Elmer UV/Vis-spectrometer Lambda 750S. The measurement range was adjusted for this set of samples to 1000 – 1400 nm, with a step size of 1 nm.

Results and discussion:

Chemical composition and phase content in $Cu_2ZnSn(S_xSe_{1-x})_4$ monograins

The presence of a very small amount of $ZnS_{0.87}Se_{0.13}$ secondary phase was detected in all 6 samples. Figure 2 (left) presents a back scatter electron (BSE) micrograph showing the homogeneity of the CZTSSe main phase alongside with the presence of the secondary phase exemplarily for the sample C15Q. All of the samples look very similar. The main quaternary phase was found to be chemically homogeneous, with slightly off-stoichiometric composition (see Figure 2, right). The presence of a $ZnS_{0.87}Se_{0.13}$ secondary phase is in a good agreement with the resulting Cu poor/Zn rich composition of the main CZTSSe phase of the monograins [25]. The Cu/(Zn+Sn), Zn/Sn and S/(S+Se) ratios of the CZTSSe phase as well as the off-stoichiometry type information and final chemical formulae of the quaternary compound, calculated according to the method described in [15, 17], are presented in Table I. As it can be seen in Figure 2 (right), the resulting composition of the CZTSSe phase in the initial sample (C15) is very close to the composition of the CZTSSe phase in the other samples resulting from

grinding, “disordering” and “ordering” procedures. All of these compositions are within the 2% measurements error, shown as a grey circle in Figure 2 (right), which confirms no significant difference in chemical composition and phase content in neither ground nor annealed (“ordered” or “disordered”) CZTSSe.

In addition to the detailed WDX analysis, Raman scattering spectra measured under the 532 nm excitation wavelength allowed to estimate the anions ratio. The measured spectra are characterized by three intense Raman peaks at 222, 235 and 330 cm^{-1} and less intense peaks at 142, 162, 193, 285 and 360 cm^{-1} . Similar spectra have been previously observed for CZTSSe compounds [26]. No significant difference was found in the spectra measured in different points of each sample, the average spectra can be seen in Figure 3. The S/(S+Se) ratio of the studied CZTSSe was estimated by taking into account the integrated intensities of Se-Se and S-Se related peaks (150 – 260 cm^{-1} spectral range – highlighted with blueish colour in Figure 3) as well as S-S related peaks (270 – 380 cm^{-1} spectral range – highlighted with yellowish colour Figure 3) as employed by Dimitrievska et al [27]. The error was estimated as standard deviation of the calculated anions ratio from the Raman spectra measured in different points of a sample. A good correlation of the resulting anionic composition calculated from the Raman spectra of the analysed material and the WDX data is established, and the slight deviations are inside the measurement errors of both techniques (seen Table I).

Cation distribution model in $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSn}(\text{S}_x\text{Se}_{1-x})_4$ monograins

An example of the neutron powder diffraction pattern and corresponding Rietveld analysis for the sample C15 in space group $I\bar{4}$ is shown in Figure 4. A good fit was obtained reaching an R_{Bragg} value of 2.12 % (see the determined structural parameters in Table II). The average neutron scattering length analysis method [28] was applied to determine the distribution of the cations Cu^+ , Zn^{2+} and Sn^{4+} on the four structural sites of the kesterite type structure ($2a$, $2b$, $2c$ and $2d$). The experimental average neutron scattering lengths (b) were calculated according to Eqs. 1 using the cation site occupancy values SOF_{2a} , SOF_{2c} , SOF_{2d} and SOF_{2b} determined by Rietveld analysis of neutron diffraction data:

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{b}_{2a}(\text{exp}) &= \text{SOF}_{2a} \cdot b_{\text{Cu}} \\ \bar{b}_{2c}(\text{exp}) &= \text{SOF}_{2c} \cdot b_{\text{Cu}} \\ \bar{b}_{2b}(\text{exp}) &= \text{SOF}_{2d} \cdot b_{\text{Zn}} \\ \bar{b}_{2b}(\text{exp}) &= \text{SOF}_{2b} \cdot b_{\text{Sn}}\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

The details of cation distribution model, which is introduced for each of the CZTSSe phases in the different samples can be found in [15] and the result can be seen in Figure 5. It is important that the sum of a cation species on the different cation sites should be in good agreement with the chemical composition of the phase determined by WDX analysis. In the case of deficit of a cation species, e. g. the sum of a cation species determined by WDX is less than 4, vacancies are assumed. Taking into account the experimentally determined total amounts of each element, as obtained by WDX analysis, and assuming that all four cation sites are fully occupied (including vacancies), the respective cation occupancy of the sites can be derived with high reliability. The resulting cation distributions for as-grown monograins (samples C15, C15Q and C15S) are presented in Figure 6 top, and for the ground ones (samples C15g, C15gQ and C15gS) in Figure 6 bottom. The detailed cation distribution as well as each of the defects in fractions of a site are presented in Table III.

Intrinsic cation point defects in $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSn}(\text{S}_x\text{Se}_{1-x})_4$ monograins

In the case of the Cu-poor/Zn-rich kesterite phase the off-stoichiometry types A, B, G and L [15] can be possible. Based on the results of the WDX measurements all six CZTSSe monograins can be located between the A and B off-stoichiometry type. The defect complexes expected would be A type: $V_{Cu} + Zn^{2+}_{Cu}$ and B type: $2Zn^{2+}_{Cu} + Zn^{2+}_{Sn}$ [15] (A-B type mixtures). Summarising both types and paying attention to the location of the monograins in the cation ratio plot closer to the B type line, we can expect the defects belonging to the B type to be more pronounced in these CZTSSe materials. The slightly lower than expected value at the 2a site (see Figure 5) is mainly due to the presence of copper vacancies V_{Cu} and Zn_{Cu} anti sites (the transition of zinc from the 2c to the 2a site forming Zn_{Cu} anti site defects is very typical for kesterites with an off-stoichiometry very close to the B-type line [14]). The Zn_{Sn} anti site defect is responsible for a slightly lower than expected average neutron scattering length value at the 2b site. The concentration of obtained point defects is very low (see Figure 6 and Table III). Comparing the fraction values for the V_{Cu} , Zn_{Cu} and Zn_{Sn} defects (Table III), it becomes clear that neither the grinding nor the “ordering” or “disordering” procedures introduce significant changes in the intrinsic point defect scenario, which is in a very good agreement with the fact that no changes in chemical composition happened either.

Cu/Zn disorder in $Cu_2ZnSn(S_xSe_{1-x})_4$ monograins

It can be observed that the experimental average neutron scattering lengths of the 2c and 2d positions significantly deviate from values expected ($b_{Cu}=7.718$ fm and $b_{Zn}=5.680$ fm) according to the kesterite type structure cation occupancy with Cu on 2c and Zn on 2d, as exemplarily shown in the average neutron scattering length analysis of the CZTSSe phase in the sample C15 (see Figure 5) The same scenario is valid for the CZTSSe phase in all the other samples. The average neutron scattering length value for the 2c site is significantly lower, and the one for 2d is significantly higher than the expected neutron scattering length on these sites. Such differences can be explained by the formation of intrinsic point defects. For instance, zinc on copper anti-site defects (Zn_{Cu}) would decrease the average neutron scattering length of the 2c crystallographic site because the neutron scattering length of zinc ($b_{Zn}=5.680$ fm) is smaller than the neutron scattering length of copper ($b_{Cu}=7.718$ fm), likewise the copper on zinc anti-site defect (Cu_{Zn}) would lead to an increase of the average neutron scattering length of the 2d site in this way forming the Cu/Zn disorder.

The intrinsic point defects the CZTSSe phase of all monograin samples resulting from the derived cation distribution in can be summarised as follows: a relatively small amount of the off-stoichiometry type related defects V_{Cu} , Zn_{Cu} and Zn_{Sn} are always present as well as significant Cu/Zn disorder expressed by Cu_{Zn} and Zn_{Cu} anti site defects involving the structural sites 2c and 2d. The detailed cation distribution of the structural sites as well as the intrinsic point defects are presented in Table III. The defect concentration related to Cu/Zn disorder (Figure 7 top) is almost an order of magnitude higher than each of the other off-stoichiometry type related defects. Comparing couples of as-grown and ground monograins, no significant change in the defect scenario as well as the Cu/Zn disorder can be noticed (C15 vs. C15g, C15Q vs. C15gQ and C15S vs. C15gS). Thus, the mechanical treatment (grinding) of the CZTSSe monograins does not influence the Cu/Zn disorder related anti site defects (Cu_{Zn} and Zn_{Cu}).

Interestingly the concentration of Cu_{Zn} and Zn_{Cu} anti site defects related to Cu/Zn disorder differs significantly within the annealed (“ordered” and “disordered”) CZTSSe monograins. Comparing “ordered” and “disordered” monograins (e. g. C15Q vs. C15S), a significant difference can be noticed. The “ordered” monograins show a decrease in Cu/Zn disorder, while in the “disordered” monograins the Cu/Zn disorder increases drastically. This is in agreement with a previously published study by anomalous X-ray diffraction [10], and confirms the assumption, that the thermal annealing used in this work allows to control the Cu/Zn disorder in CZTSSe in a very targeted way.

Using the site occupancy factors of the structural sites $2c$ and $2d$, the order parameter of Cu/Zn disorder can be calculated. This order parameter Q is defined in such a way that $Q = 0$ indicates complete disorder and $Q = 1$ indicates order. In literature different approaches can be found [1, 10, 29] depending on whether the copper site $2a$ is included and how vacancies are treated. For the kesterite-type CZTSSe phases studied here, the approach discussed in [10] was used, the same way as applied for stoichiometric CZTSSe powder samples [1]. Thus Eq. 2 was adapted from [10]

$$Q = \frac{[Cu_{2c}+Zn_{2d}]-[Zn_{2c}+Cu_{2d}]}{[Cu_{2c}+Zn_{2d}]+[Zn_{2c}+Cu_{2d}]}. \quad (2)$$

The order parameter Q was calculated for the CZTSSe phase in all of the samples and is presented in Table II and Figure 7 (bottom). Analysing the Q value shows that the “disordering” procedure increases the disorder with almost a factor of two, while the “ordering” procedure decreases the disorder, bringing the value of the order parameter Q of quenched CZTSSe monograins (sample C15gQ) to 0.76, which is highest reported for CZTSSe with $S/(S+Se)=0.62$.

As seen in the discussions above, the determination of the order parameter Q is not straightforward and requires specific analytical techniques that superimpose specific conditions on the sample. In this regard, the development of a methodology enabling an estimation of the Cu/Zn disorder level, that is based on a simple, easily accessible analytical technique that does not require any specific sample preparation and can be applied both for powder and thin film samples is of the outmost important for the whole scientific community. Previously, analysis of the Raman spectra of CZTS and CZTSe compounds allowed to develop a methodology for the assessment of the order parameter using changes in different features of the Raman spectra [9,30]. A more detailed analysis of the Raman spectra of the as-grown and treated CZTSSe monograins shows clearly a significant difference in the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the Raman peaks in the as-grown, “disordered” and “ordered” CZTSSe (Figure 3). From the series of the Raman peaks the A-like symmetry mode at 330 cm^{-1} related to pure S-S vibrations is the most isolated one and is easy to use for FWHM determination. The obtained dependency of the FWHM of the Raman peak at 330 cm^{-1} from the order parameter Q , determined from the cation distribution obtained by neutron diffraction, shows a clear possibility to develop a methodology of a Cu/Zn disorder assessment based only on the spectroscopic investigation (Figure 8). However, it should be noted that a change of other parameters, like crystalline quality or point defect concentrations, may result in a similar variation in the FWHM of the Raman peaks as has been previously observed in different kesterite type compounds [14]. Thus a further investigation with a bigger set of samples (with a more gradual change of order parameter Q and with different anion ratios) should be evaluated in order to establish a more robust methodology for the Cu/Zn disorder estimation. Nevertheless, the presented results show the high potential of Raman spectroscopy to be applied for the development of such a methodology.

Optoelectronic properties

In an attempt to correlate the obtained point defect concentrations to the optoelectronic properties of these materials, the optical band gap energy E_g was determined by diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS). Tauc plots were obtained by plotting $(F(R) \cdot hv)^2$ versus the photon energy [31], the linear part of the curve was extrapolated to the baseline, and the optical band gap was extracted from the value of intersection. An estimation of the band gap energy in the same way was previously reported for CZTS, CZTSe and CZGSe powders [32], approving the applicability of this approach. The Tauc plot derived from DRS spectra is shown in Fig. 9 (left). It is found that the band gap energy of CZTSSe monograins is changing in the range of 1.05 eV to 1.24 eV, implying no noticeable effects when comparing as-grown vs ground monograins. In this way it was confirmed, that the mechanical

treatment (grinding) has no significant influence on E_g in CZTSSe monograins. The situation changes drastically for the CZTSSe monograins which underwent a thermal treatment as the “ordering” and “disordering” procedure (see Figure 9, right). The band gap energy of “disordered” CZTSSe undergoes a red shift of an average of 50 meV in comparison to the band gap energy of as-grown CZTSSe. While for the “ordered” CZTSSe the changes in E_g are stronger and in the opposite direction (blue shift of ~ 0.1 eV). The obtained E_g values can be found in the Table IV. Similar results on the band gap variation in ordered and disordered CZTSSe have been published for CZTSSe polycrystalline thin films with $Se/(S+Se) = 0.92$ and $Se/(S+Se) = 1.0$ [11, 13], although in those reports the order parameter has not been determined experimentally.

Conclusions:

Neutron powder diffraction, wavelength dispersive X-ray spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy and diffuse reflectance spectroscopy were used to investigate the influence of mechanical (grinding) as well as thermal (“ordering” and “disordering” procedure) treatments of CZTSSe monograins. These studies show very similar chemical composition of the CZTSSe and phase content (secondary phases) as well as an off-stoichiometry type related intrinsic point defect scenario for the monograins which underwent the mechanical treatment proving lack of the influence of grinding to these specific properties. The same was found for the CZTSSe monograins which underwent a thermal treatment with one exception – the Cu/Zn disorder. The “ordering” and “disordering” procedures showed a significant impact on the order parameter Q in CZTSSe, which was directly evaluated from the neutron powder diffraction data analysis. This yielded the possibility to control the level of disorder in CZTSSe by changing the cooling rate after the low temperature annealing. Detailed analysis of the Raman spectra also showed variation in the FWHM of the Raman peaks with varying Cu/Zn disorder. The clear dependence of this parameter on the order parameter Q suggests the possibility to develop a fast and easy methodology to estimate the level of Cu/Zn disorder. In case of the optoelectronic properties the “ordering” and “disordering” procedures led to increase and decrease of the materials’ band gap energy, respectively, as revealed by the analysis of the DR spectra. Finally, the present work allowed to clearly define the independence of the main structural, compositional and optoelectronic properties of the kesterite monograins from the mechanical treatment (grinding procedure), and significant variations of some of the CZTSSe properties depending on the cooling rate after the low temperature annealing procedure.

Acknowledgements:

A portion of this research used resources at the Spallation Neutron Source, a DOE Office of Science User Facility operated by the Oak Ridge National Laboratory (IPTS-26264 for POWGEN experiment). This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreements no 777968 (INFINITE-CELL project) and 952982 (Custom-Art project). Authors from IREC belong to the SEMS (Solar Energy Materials and Systems) Consolidated Research Group of the “Generalitat de Catalunya” (ref. 2017 SGR 862) and are grateful to European Regional Development Funds (ERDF, FEDER Programa Competitivitat de Catalunya 2007–2013). M.G. acknowledges the financial support from Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities within the Juan de la Cierva fellowship (IJC2018-038199-I). DM also acknowledges the European Regional Development Fund and Archimedes/DoRa project TK141.

References:

1. G. Gurieva, D. M. Többens, S. Levenco, T. Unold, S. Schorr, Cu/Zn disorder in stoichiometric $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSn}(\text{S}_{1-x}\text{Se}_x)_4$ semiconductors: A complementary neutron and anomalous X-ray diffraction study, *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 846 (2020) 156304. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2020.156304>.
2. J. Zhou, X. Xu, B. Duan, H. Wu, J. Shi, Y. Luo, D. Li, Q. Meng, Regulating crystal growth via organic lithium salt additive for efficient Kesterite solar cells, *Nano Energy*, 89B (2021) 106405. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2021.106405>
3. S. Schorr, H.-J. Höbler, M. Tovar, A neutron diffraction study of the stannite-kesterite solid solution series, *Europ. Jour. Mineral.*, 19 (2007) 65 – 73. <https://doi.org/10.1127/0935-1221/2007/0019-0065>
4. S. Schorr, The crystal structure of kesterite type compounds: A neutron and X-ray diffraction study, *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, 95 (2011) 1482. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2011.01.002>
5. X. Liu, Y. Feng, H. Cui, F. Liu, X. Hao, G. Conibeer, D.B. Mitzi, and M. Green, The current status and future prospects of kesterite solar cells: a brief review, *Prog. Photovolt: Res. Appl.*, 24 (2016) 879–898. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pip.2741>
6. G. Rey, G. Larramona, S. Bourdais, C. Choné, B. Delatouche, A. Jacob, G. Dennler, S. Siebentritt, On the origin of band-tails in kesterite, *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, 179 (2018) 142–151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2017.11.005>
7. S. Bourdais, C. Chon, B. Delatouche, A. Jacob, G. Larramona, C. Moisan, A. Lafond, F. Donatini, G. Rey, S. Siebentritt, A. Walsh, G. Dennler, Is the Cu/Zn Disorder the Main Culprit for the Voltage Deficit in Kesterite Solar Cells?, *Adv. Energy Mater.*, 6 (2016) 1502276 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/aenm.201502276>
8. Y. E. Romanyuk, S. G. Haass, S. Giraldo, M. Placidi, D. Tiwari, D. J. Fermin, X. Hao, H. Xin, T. Schnabel, M. Kauk-Kuusik, P. Pistor, S. Lie and L. H. Wong, Doping and alloying of kesterites, *J. Phys. Energy*, 1 (2019) 044004. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/2515-7655/ab23bc>
9. J. J. S. Scragg, L. Choubac, A. Lafond, T. Ericson, and C. Platzer-Björkman, A low-temperature order-disorder transition in $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_4$ thin films, *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, 104 (2014) 041911. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4863685>
10. D. M. Többens, G. Gurieva, S. Levenco, T. Unold, S. Schorr, Temperature dependency of Cu/Zn ordering in CZTSe kesterites determined by anomalous diffraction, *Physica Status Solidi B*, 253 (2016), 1890-1897. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pssb.201600372>
11. G. Rey, A. Redinger, J. Sendler, T. P. Weiss, M. Thevenin, M. Guennou, B. El Adib. and S. Siebentritt, The band gap of $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$: Effect of order-disorder, *Applied Physics Letters*, 105 (2014) 112106. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4896315>
12. S. Schorr, G. Gonzalez-Aviles, In-situ investigation of the structural phase transition in kesterite, *Phys. Stat. Solidi A*, 206 (2009) 1054. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pssa.200881214>
13. C. Krammer, C. Huber, C. Zimmermann, M. Lang, T. Schnabel, T. Abzieher, E. Ahlswede, H. Kalt, & M. Hetterich, Reversible order-disorder related band gap changes in $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSn}(\text{S},\text{Se})_4$ via post-annealing of solar cells measured by electroreflectance, *Applied Physics Letters*, 105 (2014) 262104. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4905351>
14. Schorr, S., G. Gurieva, M. Guc, M. Dimitievska, A. Perez-Rodriguez, V. Izquierdo-Roca, C. Schnohr, J. Kim, W. Jo, J. M. Merino, Point defects, compositional fluctuations, secondary phases in non-stoichiometric kesterites, *J. Phys. Energy*, 2 (2020) 012002. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2515-7655/ab4a25/>

15. G. Gurieva, L.E. Valle Rios, A. Franz, P. Whitfield, S. Schorr, Intrinsic point defects in off-stoichiometric $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$: A neutron diffraction study, *Journal of Applied Physics*, 123 (2018) 161519/1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4997402>
16. S. Siebentritt, S. Schorr, Kesterites—a challenging material for solar cells, *Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications*, 20 (2012) 512. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pip.2156>
17. R. Gunder, J. Márquez Prieto, G. Gurieva, T. Unold, S. Schorr, Structural characterization of off-stoichiometric kesterite-type $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnGeSe}_4$ compound semiconductors: from cation distribution to intrinsic point defect density, *CrystEngComm*, 20 (2018) 1491. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7CE02090B>
18. G. Gurieva, D. M. Toebbens, M. Ya. Valakh, S. Schorr, Cu-Zn disorder in $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnGeSe}_4$: A complementary neutron diffraction and Raman spectroscopy study, *Journal of Physics and Chemistry of Solids*, 99 (2016) 100-104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpccs.2016.08.017>
19. G. Gurieva, J. A. Marquez, A. Franz, C. J. Hages, S. Levchenko, T. Unold, S. Schorr, Effect of Ag incorporation on structure and optoelectronic properties of $(\text{Ag}_{1-x}\text{Cu}_x)_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$ solid solutions, *Physical Review Materials*, 4 (2020) 054602/1-8. doi:10.1103/physrevmaterials.4.054602
20. D. Meissner, K. Ernits, S. Gahr, L. Kapitan, M. Vetter, C. Glatz, R. Syed, Kesterite based monograin photovoltaics: the ideal solution for sustainable power supply, *Solar Energy Materials and Solar cells*, submitted.
21. E. Mellikov, M. Altosaar, M. Kauk - Kuusik, K. Timmo, D. Meissner, M. Grossberg, J. Krustok and O. Volobujeva, Growth of CZTS-Based Monograins and Their Application to Membrane Solar Cells, in: K. Ito (Eds.), *Copper Zinc Tin Sulfide-Based Thin-Film Solar Cells*, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd., 2015, pp. 289-309. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118437865.ch13>
22. A. Huq, M. J. Kirkham, P.F. Peterson, J.P. Hodges, P. Whitfield, K. Page, T. Huegle, E. B. Iverson, A. Parizzi, G.Q. Rennich, POWGEN: rebuild of a third-generation powder diffractometer at the Spallation Neutron Source, *J. Appl. Cryst.* 52 (2019) 52 1189- 1201. <https://doi.org/10.1107/S160057671901121X>
23. H.M. Rietveld, A profile refinement method for nuclear and magnetic structures, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.*, 2 (1969) 65-71. <https://doi.org/10.1107/S0021889869006558>
24. Juan Rodriguez-Carvajal and Thierry Roisnel, www.ill.eu/sites/fullprof/
25. L. E. Valle Rios, K. Neldner, G. Gurieva and S. Schorr, Existence of off-stoichiometric single phase kesterite, *J. Alloy Compd.*, 657 (2016) 408. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2015.09.198>
26. M. Dimitrievska, H. Xie, A. Fairbrother, X. Fontane, G. Gurieva, E. Saucedo, A. Perez-Rodriguez, S. Schorr, V. Izquierdo-Roca, Multiwavelength excitation Raman scattering of $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSn}(\text{S}_x\text{Se}_{1-x})_4$ ($0 \leq x \leq 1$) polycrystalline thin films: Vibrational properties of sulfoselenide solid solutions, *Applied Physics Letters*, 105(2014) 031913. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4891333>
27. M. Dimitrievska, G. Gurieva, H. Xie, A. Carrete, A. Cabota, E. Saucedo, A. Pérez-Rodríguez, S. Schorr, V. Izquierdo-Roca, Raman scattering quantitative analysis of the anion chemical composition in kesterite $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSn}(\text{S}_x\text{Se}_{1-x})_4$ solid solutions, *J. Alloy Compd.*, 628 (2015) 464-470. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2014.12.175>
28. S. Schorr, X-Ray and Neutron Diffraction on Materials for Thin-Film Solar Cells, in: D. Abou-Ras, T. Kirchartz, U. Rau (Eds.), *Advanced Characterization Techniques for Thin Film Solar Cells*, Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co., 2011, pp. 347.
29. A.Ritscher, M. Hölzel, & M. Lerch, The order-disorder transition in $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_4$ — A neutron scattering investigation, *Journal of Solid State Chemistry*, 238 (2016) 68 - 73. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.0c00886>
30. F. Atlan, I. Becerril-Romero, S. Giraldo, V. Rotaru, Yu. Sánchez, G. Gurieva, S. Schorr, E. Arushanov, A. Pérez-Rodríguez, V. Izquierdo-Roca, M. Guc, Stability of $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4/\text{CdS}$ heterojunction based

solar cells under soft post-deposition thermal treatments, *Solar Energy Materials and Solar cells*, submitted.

31. Tauc, J., R. Grigorovici and A. Vancu, Optical properties and electronic structure of amorphous germanium, *Physica Status Solidi*, 15 (1966) 627-637. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pssb.19660150224>
32. S. Schorr and G. Gurieva, Energy band gap variations in chalcogenide compound semiconductors: influence of crystal structure, structural disorder, and compositional variations, In: S. Schorr and C. Weidenthaler (Eds.), *Crystallography in Materials Science: From Structure-Property Relationships to Engineering*, Walter de Gruyter GmbH, Berlin/Munich/Boston, 2021, pp. 123-151. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110674910-004>

Tables:

Table I. Overview of the investigated CZTSSe monograin samples: cation ratios Cu/(Zn+Sn), Zn/Sn and anion ratio S/(S+Se) of the main phase (CZTSSe) obtained by WDX analysis, chemical formula, off-stoichiometry type and presence of secondary phases as well as the S/(S+Se) ratio. obtained from the analysis of Raman spectroscopy data.

sample name	Cu/(Zn+Sn)	Zn/Sn	S/(S+Se)	chemical formula	secondary phases	off-stoichiometry type	S/(S+Se) [Raman]
C15	0.95(2)	1.07(2)	0.62(1)	Cu _{1.95} Zn _{1.06} Sn _{0.98} S _{2.48} Se _{1.52}	ZnS _{0.87} Se _{0.13}	A-B	0.56(4)
C15g	0.95(2)	1.06(2)	0.62(1)	Cu _{1.95} Zn _{1.05} Sn _{0.99} S _{2.48} Se _{1.52}	ZnS _{0.87} Se _{0.13}	A-B	0.61(2)
C15Q	0.96(2)	1.05(2)	0.62(1)	Cu _{1.95} Zn _{1.04} Sn _{0.99} S _{2.48} Se _{1.52}	ZnS _{0.87} Se _{0.13}	A-B	0.61(2)
C15gQ	0.97(2)	1.06(2)	0.61(1)	Cu _{1.97} Zn _{1.04} Sn _{0.99} S _{2.44} Se _{1.56}	ZnS _{0.87} Se _{0.13}	A-B	0.63(2)
C15S	0.96(2)	1.07(2)	0.62(1)	Cu _{1.96} Zn _{1.06} Sn _{0.98} S _{2.48} Se _{1.52}	ZnS _{0.87} Se _{0.13}	A-B	0.61(4)
C15gS	0.97(2)	1.07(2)	0.62(1)	Cu _{1.96} Zn _{1.05} Sn _{0.99} S _{2.48} Se _{1.52}	ZnS _{0.87} Se _{0.13}	A-B	0.62(2)

Table II The structural results obtained from the refinements against neutron powder diffraction data (lattice parameters, atomic positions, site occupancy factors, isotropic temperature factors (B_{iso}), and R_{Bragg}).

sample name		C15	C15g	C15Q	C15gQ	C15S	C15gS
Lattice parameters (Å)	a	5.533 (1)	5.533 (1)	5.533 (1)	5.533 (1)	5.535 (1)	5.535 (1)
	c	11.035 (3)	11.035 (3)	11.041 (3)	11.041 (3)	11.029 (3)	11.029 (3)
SOF	Cu $2a$	0.933 (10)	0.931 (11)	0.934 (10)	0.954 (10)	0.996 (9)	0.979 (10)
	Cu $2c$	0.963 (9)	0.949 (12)	0.948 (12)	0.951 (12)	0.956 (11)	0.967 (9)
	Zn $2d$	1.097 (10)	1.123 (13)	1.134 (13)	1.138 (13)	1.045 (9)	1.035 (9)
	Sn $2b$	0.999 (9)	0.999 (10)	0.999 (10)	0.999 (10)	0.996 (12)	0.999 (12)
anion position	x	0.7567 (11)	0.7565 (13)	0.7563 (13)	0.7567 (13)	0.7552 (9)	0.7562 (10)
	y	0.7606 (7)	0.7610 (8)	0.7610 (8)	0.7607 (9)	0.7616(4)	0.7616 (5)
	z	0.8708 (1)	0.8710 (1)	0.8707 (1)	0.8707 (1)	0.8713 (1)	0.8717 (2)
B_{iso} (Å ²)	$2a, 2c, 2d$	1.672 (19)	1.699 (18)	1.680 (19)	1.690 (20)	1.671 (19)	1.681 (18)
	$2b$	0.626 (36)	0.620 (36)	0.681 (38)	0.699 (41)	0.479 (36)	0.481 (35)
	$8g$	0.821 (16)	0.822 (16)	0.813 (16)	0.831 (17)	0.792 (18)	0.807 (17)

R_{Bragg} (%)		2.12	2.18	2.17	1.84	2.13	1.87
-----------------	--	------	------	------	------	------	------

Table III The modelled cation distribution (in site fractions), intrinsic point defects (in site fractions) and the order parameter Q as a quantitative measure of disorder of all investigated CZTSSe monograins. V indicated vacancies.

sample name	2a			2c		2d		2b		V_{Cu}	Zn_{Cu}	Zn_{Sn}	Cu/Zn	Q
	V	Cu	Zn	Cu	Zn	Cu	Zn	Zn	Sn					
C15	0.010	0.780	0.210	0.876	0.124	0.290	0.710	0.017	0.983	0.01	0.044	0.017	0.290	0.42
C15g	0.017	0.795	0.188	0.810	0.190	0.340	0.660	0.011	0.989	0.017	0.038	0.011	0.340	0.32
C15Q	0.015	0.783	0.202	0.800	0.200	0.370	0.630	0.008	0.992	0.015	0.032	0.008	0.370	0.26
C15gQ	0.001	0.810	0.189	0.795	0.205	0.365	0.635	0.014	0.986	0.001	0.029	0.014	0.365	0.27
C15S	0.001	0.999	0.000	0.833	0.167	0.130	0.870	0.018	0.982	0.001	0.037	0.018	0.130	0.74
C15gS	0.003	0.943	0.054	0.900	0.100	0.120	0.880	0.015	0.985	0.003	0.034	0.015	0.120	0.76

Table IV Optical bangap energy of CZTSSe monograins obtained from diffuse reflectance.

sample name	E_g , eV
C15	1.11(8)
C15g	1.14(3)
C15Q	1.05(5)
C15gQ	1.10(3)
C15S	1.22(4)
C15gS	1.24(4)

Figures

Figure1. The scheme of the grinding experiment (C15 – as-grown, C15g – ground samples). The point where the “disordered” CZTSSe samples C15Q and C15gQ were taken out of the furnace is marked with the red arrow in the graph showing the annealing procedure. The “ordering” slow annealing procedure resulted in samples C15S and C15gS.

Figure 2. BSE micrograph of the sample C15Q with highlighted ZnS_{0.87}Se_{0.13} and CZTSSe phases (left) and the cation ratio plot showing all C15X monograins (right). All points are located in the Cu-poor/Zn-rich area corresponding to the off-stoichiometry type mixture A-B .

Figure 3. Raman spectra of CZTSSe monograin samples measured under 532 nm excitation wavelength.

Figure 4. Rietveld refinement against the neutron powder diffraction data of the sample C15 in space group $I\bar{4}$. The red dots are experimental data, the black line is the obtained fit, the blue ticks are the Bragg peak positions of the kesterite type structure and the blue line is the difference between the experimental and calculated intensities. A good fit was obtained reaching an R_{Bragg} value of 2.12 %.

Figure 5. Average neutron scattering length \bar{b} of the cation sites $2a$, $2c$, $2d$ and $2b$ for the CZTSSe phase in the sample C15, (full symbols – experimental values; star – calculated values according to the most suitable cation distribution model; lines – neutron scattering length of the elements Cu, Sn and Zn).

Figure 6. The resulting cation distribution on the structural sites 2a, 2b, 2c and 2d of the Kesterite-type structure for (top) as grow (C15, C15Q and C15S) CZTSSe monograins and (bottom) ground (C15g, C15gQ and C15gS) CZTSSe monograins, obtained from the in-depth analysis of neutron powder diffraction data.

Figure 7. Comparison of the concentration of intrinsic point defects (top) and the order parameter Q of the Cu/Zn disorder (bottom) in as grown, "ordered" and "disordered" CZTSSe monograins which have not been ground (closed symbols) and ground (open symbols), respectively.

Figure 8. Dependency of FWHM of the Raman peak around 330 cm^{-1} on the order parameter Q in CZTSSe monograins. The error bars have been calculated as standard deviations in the FWHM of the peak at 330 cm^{-1} in the spectra measured in different points of each monograin sample.

Figure 9. Tauc plots for the band gap energy determination of the as-grown monograins (left); Comparison of the E_g in as-grown, "ordered" and "disordered" CZTSSe monograins which have not been ground (closed symbols) and ground (open symbols), respectively (right).

This manuscript has been authored by UT-Battelle, LLC, under contract DE-AC05-00OR22725 with the US Department of Energy (DOE). The US government retains and the publisher, by accepting the article for publication, acknowledges that the US government retains a nonexclusive, paid-up, irrevocable, worldwide license to publish or reproduce the published form of this manuscript, or allow others to do so, for US government purposes. DOE will provide public access to these results of federally sponsored research in accordance with the DOE Public Access Plan.
